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Effect of Mobile-Augmented-Reality on Performance in Algebra Concept among Secondary School Mathematics Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of Mobile-Augmented-Reality on Performance in Algebra Concept among Secondary School Mathematics Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The research aimed to determine whether MAR enhances students' academic outcomes in algebra and whether gender differences exist in performance when using MAR. A pretest-posttest non-equivalent quasi-experimental design was used. The study population comprised all SSII students in the zone during the 2023/2024 academic session, totaling 12,333. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 103 students from two schools, with simple random sampling employed to assign schools into experimental (51 students) and control (52 students) groups. The Mobile Augmented Reality Algebra Performance Test (MARAPT) was the instrument used for data collection. Its reliability was confirmed with a KR-20 coefficient of 0.87. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to address the research questions, while ANCOVA tested the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed a significant improvement in algebra performance among students taught with MAR compared to those taught with conventional methods. However, no significant gender-based performance difference was found within the MAR group. The study concluded that MAR positively influences students' algebra performance regardless of gender. It recommended the integration of MAR into the mathematics curriculum to boost student engagement and learning outcomes. Furthermore, it advised the Zamfara State government to train mathematics teachers on effective MAR implementation to enhance instructional quality in secondary schools.

Keywords: Augmented Reality (AR), Mobile Augmented Reality (MAR), Algebra, Performance.

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Introduction

Mathematics education is vital for a nation's scientific and technological progress, serving as a gateway to success in various fields, especially the sciences and social sciences. To pursue further studies, secondary school students must achieve credit-level proficiency in mathematics, underscoring the necessity of a solid mathematical foundation for academic and career success (Fitzmaurice et al., 2021). Sodangi et al. (2021) indicate that inadequate instructional materials, unqualified teachers, and ineffective teaching methods contribute to students' poor performance in mathematics. This paper focuses on teaching strategies since research shows that instructional approaches significantly impact learning outcomes (Isah et al., 2020).

Traditional teaching methods often rely on a "talk and chalk" approach, leading to student difficulty in understanding concepts while copying from the board. Such methods can also exhaust teachers, highlighting the need for more engaging, efficient, and technologically integrated instructional strategies, particularly for abstract subjects like algebra.

The education sector is experiencing a methodological shift due to technological advancements, which have facilitated innovative teaching methods and enabled student participation in the learning process (Kolster, 2021). Emerging technologies in education, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and Augmented Reality (AR), are transforming learning experiences (Fitria et al., 2022). AR enhances classroom teaching by making learning more flexible and simplifying complex concepts like algebra (Hamzah et al., 2021).

Mobile Augmented Reality (MAR), leveraging mobile devices, offers accessible and interactive learning experiences. It enhances algebra learning by providing portable resources, bridging classroom education with real-world applications (Fabian et al., 2018). The integration of mobile technologies fosters cooperative learning environments and accommodates diverse mathematics learning styles, contributing positively to student engagement and understanding (Polydoros, 2021). Overall, adopting innovative teaching strategies and technologies like MAR can significantly improve student outcomes in mathematics education.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

A review of various studies on MAR indicates generally positive impacts on students' academic performance, spatial skills, motivation, and anxiety levels in mathematics education, although findings vary across different contexts and methodologies. Gün and Atasoy (2017) found improvements in spatial abilities among students exposed to AR, but the differences between the experimental and control groups lacked statistical significance. Jamali (2017) highlighted that MAR enhanced learning outcomes and self-efficacy, with no notable gender differences observed. Similarly, Wahyu et al. (2020) reported MAR's beneficial effects on scientific literacy, academic achievement, and learning retention, confirming its potential in enhancing students' educational experiences. In contrast, Mehmet and Yasemin (2021) noted improvements in academic performance but found no significant effects on anxiety or motivation, suggesting that while MAR may boost grades, it does not necessarily alleviate related mental barriers.

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Further investigations by Tekeate and Samuel (2018) and Olanrewaju et al. (2021) demonstrated that both traditional and indigenous games significantly improved mathematics achievement, also revealing no gender disparities in performance. Studies by Saundarajan et al. (2020) and Cetintav and Yilmaz (2022) corroborated these findings, indicating that MAR applications like Photomath positively impacted students' understanding of algebra and geometry, thereby enhancing academic performance and fostering self-regulated learning practices. Likewise, Guntur and Setyaningrum (2021) reported advancements in spatial and problem-solving skills, along with positive shifts in learning attitudes associated with MAR interventions.

However, research by Maffei (2020), Omurtak and Zeybek (2022), and Pinder (2022) indicated a lack of significance in performance differences, suggesting that the success of MAR may be contingent upon specific implementation strategies and the context within which it is applied. Contrastingly, Amores-Valencia et al. (2023) and Abu Ziden et al. (2022) provided evidence for improved academic performance linked to MAR's use in educational settings. Gender differences across these studies typically remained insignificant, reinforcing the notion that MAR benefits all students regardless of gender.

A notable limitation in existing research was identified in the study by Olaronke and Olusola (2024), where they reported improved performance in MAR-integrated classrooms but faced methodological challenges. Specifically, the use of a descriptive survey instead of an experimental design and the sampling of non-equivalent student levels undermined the robustness of their findings. This gap underscores the necessity for more rigorous research approaches, as reflected in the current study's aim to employ a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design with uniform sample levels, ensuring the validity of its findings.

In summary, the reviewed literature strongly supports the use of MAR in enhancing academic achievement, particularly in mathematics. Despite the overall positive trends, the variability in results emphasizes the influence of differences in study design, implementation techniques, and assessment tools. Most studies align with the current research focus, providing critical insights while identifying methodological gaps that the present study seeks to address. The findings underscore the need for further investigation into the optimal use of MAR in diverse educational contexts to maximize its potential benefits for students' learning outcomes.

Statement of the Research Problem

The teaching strategy employed in secondary school mathematics significantly impacts students' success, particularly in algebra. Despite the potentials of well-trained teachers and interactive resources like technology to foster an engaging, student-centered learning environment, many Nigerian students continue to struggle with algebra due to inadequate teaching methods, lack of interactive tools, and insufficient practice opportunities. Reports from WAEC indicate persistent low performance in mathematics, particularly in simplifying equations involving fractions. Although research on AR in mathematics education is on the increase, studies focusing specifically on algebra remain limited, especially in Nigeria's northwestern regions. This study aims to address these gaps by investigating effect of MAR on performance in algebra concept

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among secondary school mathematics students in Gusau Educational Zone (GEZ), Zamfara state, Nigeria highlighting the potentials of innovative teaching strategies to enhance mathematics education.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine the investigating effect of MAR on performance in algebra concept among secondary school mathematics students in GEZ, Zamfara state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. find the effect of MAR on the students' performance in algebra; and
- ii. determine the effect of MAR on the male and female students' performance in algebra.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of students taught algebra using MAR and those taught same content using the conventional method?
2. What is the difference between the mean pretest and posttest algebra scores of the male and female students taught algebra using MAR intervention?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of students taught algebra using MAR and those taught same content using the conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest algebra scores of male and female students taught algebra using MAR intervention.

Methodology

This study adopted the pretest – posttest quasi experimental non – equivalent control group design. The population involved all the 1233 SSII students in GEZ of Zamfara State during the 2023 – 2024 academic session gotten from the Education Quality Assurance Authority, Ministry of Education, Science and Technology. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 103 students from two schools, while simple random technique was employed to categorized the schools into experimental and control (51 experimental class and 52 control). The groups were pretested before the treatment. Mobile Augmented Reality Algebra Performance Test (MARAPT) was developed, subjected to experts' validation and reliability testing using the KR-20 and thereafter used for data collection. A reliability coefficient of 0.86 was obtained, which was considered to satisfied the internal consistency of items, and thus reliable for use in the study. After the treatment, the MARAPT was administered to both the experimental and control group. Data was collected were scored and analysed using mean, standard deviation and Analysis of Covariance for analysis through SPSS version 27.

Presentation of Results

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The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Answering the Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of students taught algebra using MAR and those taught same content using the conventional method?

Table 1

Mean Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Algebra Performance Test of Groups

Group	Pretest				Posttest			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	SEM	Mean	Std. Deviation	SEM	Mean Gain
MAR	51	7.31	1.76	0.247	11.45	3.548	0.367	4.14
Control	52	6.19	2.01	0.279	7.75	2.095	0.29	1.56
Mean Difference		1.12			3.7			

Table 1 shows that the MAR group recorded a mean gain 4.14 between the pretest ($M = 7.31$, $SD = 1.76$) and posttest ($M = 11.45$, $SD = 3.55$) while the control group recorded a mean gain of 1.56 between the pretest ($M = 6.19$, $SD = 2.01$) and posttest ($M = 7.75$, $SD = 2.10$) in the algebra performance test. The results as shown in Table 1 also shows that the difference between the mean posttest scores of students taught algebra using MAR ($M = 11.45$, $SD = 3.548$) and those taught same content using the conventional method ($M = 7.75$, $SD = 2.095$) was 3.7. This indicates that the intervention used in the MAR group improve the students' performance in algebra as compared to the control group.

Research Question Two: What is the mean difference between the pretest and posttest algebra scores of the male and female students taught algebra using MAR intervention?

Table 2 revealed the mean, standard deviation and mean difference of algebra performance test by gender in the experimental groups.

Table 2

Mean Difference the Pretest and Posttest Algebra Performance Test by Gender in Experimental Group

Group	Gender	Pretest				Posttest			
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	SEM	Mean	Std. Deviation	SEM	Mean Gain
MAR	Males	33	7.03	1.879	0.327	12.15	2.539	0.442	5.12
	Females	18	7.83	1.425	0.336	10.17	2.065	0.487	2.34
Mean Difference			-0.8			1.98			

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As shown in Table 2, the pretest ($M = 7.03, SD = 1.879$) and posttest ($M = 12.15, SD = 2.539$) of algebra performance test scores the male students recorded a higher mean gain (i.e., 5.12) than the mean gain (i.e., 2.34) from the pretest ($M = 7.83, SD = 1.425$) and posttest ($M = 10.17, SD = 2.065$) scores of their female counterparts. Furthermore, Table 2 shows that the difference between the mean posttest scores of the male ($M = 12.15, SD = 2.539$) and female ($M = 10.17, SD = 2.065$) students taught algebra using MAR was 1.98. This indicates that the intervention used in the MAR group improved the male students' performance in algebra as compared to their female counterparts.

Test of Assumptions for ANCOVA

The Kolmogorov – Smirnov normality test conducted to ascertain the normality of posttest scores indicates that the assumption normality is not violated, $F(103) = 0.083, p = 0.080$. Similarly, the Levene's test of equality variance conducted indicates that the posttest scores of the groups are not significant, $F(1, 101) = 0.884, p = 0.349$. Therefore, the assumption of equality of error variance was not violated. Also, no significant interaction between the groups and pretest scores was found, $F(1,103) = 5.02, p = 0.34$. Thus, the regression of slope assumption was met.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of students taught algebra using MAR and those taught same content using the conventional method.

To test this hypothesis, a one – way ANCOVA was conducted. The algebra posttest scores were used as dependent variable, while the pretest were treated as a covariate to control for initial differences.

Table 3

ANCOVA Results of Algebra Performance of MAR and the Control Groups

Dependent Variable: POSTTEST

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	354.442 ^a	2	177.221	32.422	.000	.393
Intercept	612.530	1	612.530	112.060	.000	.528
PRETEST	1.771	1	1.771	.324	.571	.003
GROUP	310.057	1	310.057	56.724	.000	.362
Error	546.607	100	5.466			
Total	10359.000	103				
Corrected Total	901.049	102				

a. R Squared = .393 (Adjusted R Squared = .381)

The ANCOVA results, as shown in Table 3, indicated a statistically significant mean difference among groups, $F(1, 103) = 56.72, p < .05, \eta^2 = .362$. The partial eta squared ($\eta^2 = .361$) indicates that approximately 36.1% of variance in posttest scores can be attributed to the groups

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differences. Although statistically substantial, this effect size is typically considered large based on Cohen’s (1988) guidelines. The estimated marginal means of algebra performance scores of the groups is shown in Table 4.

Table 4

Estimated marginal Means of Algebra Performance Scores of the Groups

Dependent Variable: POSTTEST

GROUP	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
MAR	11.411 ^a	.335	10.747	12.075
CONTROL	7.789 ^a	.331	7.132	8.446

a. Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: PRETEST = 6.75.

Table 4 shows that the MAR group (M = 11.41, SE = .34) scored significantly higher than the control group (M = 7.79, SE = .33). Since there is significant mean difference among groups ($p < .05$), the first null hypothesis was not retained. Therefore, there was significant difference between the algebra scores of the students taught using MAR and those taught same content using the conventional method.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest algebra scores of male and female students taught algebra using MAR intervention.

To test this hypothesis, a two – way ANCOVA was conducted. The algebra posttest scores were used as dependent variable, while the pretest scores were treated as a covariate to control for initial differences. The result is shown in Table 5.

Table 5

ANCOVA Results of Algebra Performance of MAR and the Control Groups

Dependent Variable: POSTTEST

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	404.195 ^a	4	101.049	19.931	.000	.449
Intercept	522.491	1	522.491	103.057	.000	.513
PRETEST	5.462	1	5.462	1.077	.302	.011
GROUP	234.374	1	234.374	46.228	.000	.321
GENDER	29.299	1	29.299	5.779	.068	.026
GROUP * GENDER	23.089	1	23.089	4.554	.235	.014
Error	496.854	98	5.070			
Total	10359.000	103				
Corrected Total	901.049	102				

a. R Squared = .449 (Adjusted R Squared = .426)

Table 5 indicates no significant interaction effect between gender and the experimental group, $F(1, 98) = 4.55, p = .235, \eta^2 = .014$. The result also revealed no significant difference between

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genders, $F(1, 98) = 5.78$, $p = .068$, $\eta^2 = .026$. Consequently, the second null hypothesis was retained.

Summary of Major Findings

- i. The students taught algebra using MAR intervention significantly outperformed those taught same content using the conventional method.
- ii. The male and female students taught algebra using MAR intervention exhibited equivalent level of performance.

Discussion of Findings

The study examined the effectiveness of MAR in improving students' algebra performance compared to conventional teaching methods. The first major finding supports the idea that interactive and engaging learning experiences, such as MAR can enhance academic outcomes. This finding aligns with numerous prior studies. For instance, Jamali (2017) and Wahyu et al. (2020) confirmed that MAR significantly improves academic performance and scientific literacy. Saundarajan et al. (2020) demonstrated that Photomath, an MAR tool, enhances algebra learning. Mehmet and Yasemin (2021) found MAR boosts achievement and motivation. Similarly, Guntur & Setyaningrum (2021) showed MAR improves learning in geometry and vectors, respectively.

Other supporting studies include Cetintav and Yilmaz (2022), who found significant gains in geometry learning and motivation; Abu Ziden et al. (2022), who reported improved achievement and engagement in science; and Amores-Valencia et al. (2023), who found AR users scored higher academically. Nigerian studies by Olaronke & Olusola (2024), Arikewuyo et al. (2021), and Tekenate & Ahiakwo (2021) confirmed MAR's positive impact on mathematics performance, regardless of gender. Studies by Lin & Cheng (2022) and Tukur et al. (2023) further validated technology-enhanced learning tools' effectiveness.

However, few studies reported no significant effects. For instance, Gün & Atasoy (2017), Maffei (2020), Omurtak & Zeybek (2022), and Pinder (2022) observed either minimal or no differences in achievement or motivation, highlighting that MAR's effectiveness can vary based on context, content, and implementation. In summary, while a few studies reported no significant effect, the bulk of research supports that MAR can enhance students' performance in mathematics, particularly algebra, by providing interactive, engaging, and effective learning experiences.

The second major finding of the study suggests that the MAR intervention benefits both genders equally, suggesting its potential for promoting equitable learning in mathematics. This finding aligns with previous studies. For instance, Muhammad (2017) and Tekenate and Samuel (2018) reported no significant gender-based differences in mathematics performance following interventions. Olanrewaju et al. (2021) similarly found no gender effect on pupils' numeracy scores, and Tukur et al. (2023) reported no gender difference in achievement scores. Ekpeyong and Ekwueme (2021) found no significant gender-based differences in student performance using spinner or dice games, although they later reported a gender difference with the dice game. Chukwurah (2022) observed improved student interest through algebraic board games but no

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gender difference in interest scores. Garba (2024) also found no significant difference in interest scores by gender using ethno mathematics and problem-based strategies. Zubairu and Uzezi (2021) reported no significant gender-based differences in Chemistry achievement using 4MAT and demonstration methods. However, Arikewuyo et al. (2021) observed that female students performed better using mobile technology strategies. Overall, the present study confirms that MAR and similar interventions effectively support both male and female students, fostering equitable academic performance.

Conclusion

The primary objective of the study was to examine the effects of mobile augmented reality on performance in algebra among secondary students in Gusau Educational Zone of Zamfara State. Students taught using MAR exhibited superior performance in algebra when contrasted with the conventional group, and results showed consistency across genders concerning algebra performance. It could therefore be concluded that the MAR intervention possesses the potentials of enhancing secondary students' performance in algebra irrespective of gender differences.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the findings, the study offered the following recommendations:

- i. Schools should integrate MAR into mathematics teaching to enhance students' engagement and improve their performance.
- ii. Mathematics teachers should be trained by the State government on the effective use of MAR delivering instruction.
- iii. Zamfara State government should provide adequate pedagogical infrastructures to support the deployment of MAR in the classroom.
- iv. Educational policy makers should promote the development of local MAR content tailored to national mathematics curriculum.

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